

Appendix D-1: Sediment Coring Investigation Description

This appendix provides additional technical descriptions of the field and analytical work performed during the 2010 Sediment Coring Investigation.

Sediment Coring Investigation

The sediment core sampling activities were conducted within the Gowanus Canal during March and April 2010. A summary of the sampling objectives, sample collection and processing methods and results, and general observations with respect to field conditions are presented in this section. The following tables and attachments are included as part of this sampling summary:

Table D1 – Sediment Coring Field Data (e.g., as-sampled coordinates, total core penetration and recovery, tide information, elevation data)

Table D2 – Thickness of Native Material Sampled

Attachment 1 – USEPA Sediment Core Logs

Attachment 2 – Sediment Core Photologs by Transect

Attachment 3 – Sediment Core Photos (CD only)

Attachment 4 – USEPA-ERT Sediment Core Logs

Sampling Objectives

Previous sediment core data collected from the Gowanus Canal by GEI Consultants Inc. (GEI) for KeySpan Corporation (now owned by National Grid) indicated that up to 20 feet of very soft, fine-grained sediment had accumulated on top of the native Gowanus Creek sediments, and that the soft accumulated sediments were highly contaminated throughout (GEI, 2007). The objectives of this sampling effort were to:

- 1) Collect sediment samples to a depth of 6 feet into the native Gowanus Creek sediments at all locations to determine the vertical extent of contamination throughout the canal.
- 2) Characterize contaminant concentrations throughout the sediment column at a subset of locations adjacent to potential sources of contamination;
- 3) confirm sampling results at a subset of locations previously sampled by GEI
- 4) provide additional spatial coverage in specific areas of the canal.

Sediment cores were collected from the following locations using vibratory coring equipment:

- 88 transect locations previously sampled by GEI
- 21 new sampling locations along 7 new transect lines
- 17 new sampling locations not located on a transect
- 9 contingency sampling locations identified by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)

Sediment samples from all locations were analyzed for target analyte list/target compound list (TAL/TCL) parameters (including mercury and cyanide), grain size, total organic carbon (TOC), and sulfide at off-site laboratories for the purpose of characterizing the nature and extent of contamination and physical characteristics of the sediments. For the new core locations not positioned on transects, one composite sample

of the entire soft sediment thickness was collected and analyzed for Toxic Characteristic Leaching Procedure (TCLP) parameters and hazardous waste characteristics to support the evaluation of remedial alternatives.

Sediment Core Collection

The sediment core collection was performed by AquaSurvey, Incorporated (ASI; Flemington, NJ) using the *R/V Manasquan*. Once the vessel was positioned on a target station, staff aboard the *R/V Manasquan* measured the water depth and determined the elevation of the sediment surface as described below. In shallow areas, along the sides of the upper and middle portions of canal, the sediment was often probed using a metal rod constructed of rigid steel conduit to determine whether debris was likely to obstruct sediment core collection. If large debris was encountered, the station location was adjusted. The sediment core was then collected using the *R/V Manasquan's* vibracore apparatus following ASI's Standard Operating Procedure (SOP). Field data (as-sampled coordinates, water depths, tide stage, and sediment surface elevation) and sediment core collection data are summarized in Table D1.

Sediment cores were collected to the maximum possible depth of 20 feet or to refusal, which was defined as less than 0.5 foot of core barrel advancement after three minutes of vibration. In instances where the core barrel did not penetrate the target depth of 6 feet into the native Gowanus Creek sediments (i.e., the vibracore was advanced to a depth of 20 feet or encountered refusal before 6 feet of native sediment was collected), the decision tree presented in *SOP-06 Sediment Core Collection, Characterization, and Processing* was used to determine if additional attempts were required. SOP-06 was included in the Gowanus Canal Phase 2 Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP). A total of 253 coring attempts were required to collect cores from 135 sampling locations.

Elevation Determination

The elevation of the sediment surface was determined using the following step-wise procedure at each sampling location:

1. Once the sampling team was on location, a calibrated and weighted line was lowered through the water column to determine water depth.
2. Real Time Ports was called to obtain the real-time tide stage at The Battery, in New York City. This tide-stage value is referenced to Mean Lower Low Water (MLLW).
3. The predicted tides (from the National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Association's *Tides and Currents* program) for The Battery and Gowanus Bay were reviewed and compared to the real-time tide information to determine a difference.
4. Due to the fact that the Gowanus tide tables are based on the Battery, it was assumed that the difference between the Battery and Gowanus were the same and the correction factor determined by the comparison of the real-time and predicted tides for the Battery was applied to the predicted Gowanus Bay tides.
5. The tidal elevation was applied to the measured water depth to provide the water depth relative to MLLW (e.g., if the corrected tide was +4.5 feet MLLW, this amount was subtracted from the measured water depth).
6. The water depth relative to MLLW was then converted to NAVD88 using a factor of 2.8 feet. This value was obtained through the tidal benchmark data from the Battery Tidal Datasheet¹.

Sediment Core Processing and Sample Collection

After collection, the cores were cut into sections of a manageable length for handling and transport from the *R/V Manasquan* to the on-shore core processing team. The cores were transferred to the processing team at several locations throughout the canal, depending upon where the sampling vessel was working. Core transfer locations included the Bayside Fuel Dock at the end of Sackett Street, the northwest corner of the

¹ http://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/data_menu.shtml?stn=8518750%20The%20Battery,%20NY&type=Datums
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Carroll Street Bridge, the 2nd Street Canoe Launch, and through the fence the end of Bond Street. Upon transfer to shore, the cores were placed upright in a refrigerator until they were processed.

The sediment cores were processed in accordance with *SOP-06 Sediment Core Collection, Characterization, and Processing*. Briefly, the cores from each location were split lengthwise using an electric slot cutter, and then photographed and described with respect to stratigraphy, sediment type, apparent grain size, color, odor, and any other notable characteristics. Each core was identified in the photographs by writing the station ID and sample interval on a dry erase board that is shown in the photographs. Cores were described according to ASTM Method D2488 (Standard Practice for Description and Identification of Soils, Visual-Manual Procedure; modified slightly to apply to sediments).

After the core characterization was completed, the core was sectioned using the following schemes:

- For cores collected from the previously sampled GEI locations, up to 3 samples (2-foot composites) of native sediment were collected from each core.
- For cores collected from the new transects and individual core locations, samples were collected continuously in 2-foot composite sample intervals from the top of the core to a depth of 6 feet into the native sediment. Soft accumulated sediment and native sediment were sampled separately.

Sediment sample intervals were generally 2 feet in length; in many cases, shorter intervals were sampled due to variable core lengths or transition zones between the native and accumulated sediment.

Samples for analysis of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and sulfide were collected from each sampling interval prior to sediment homogenization. After the collection of those aliquots, the remaining material from each sample interval was transferred to a dedicated aluminum pan and homogenized until a uniform texture and color was achieved. Sediment directly in contact with the catcher or nose cone was not included in the material that was homogenized and submitted for analytical testing. In addition, sediment from the sides of the core liner was not included as part of the samples submitted for laboratory analysis; only sediment from the central portion of the core was used.

The homogenized sediment was then transferred to the laboratory-specified bottleware, labeled and bagged for shipment to the analytical laboratories. In instances where sample volume was limited, the hierarchy presented in SOP-06 was followed to determine which analyses were requested. Upon collection, samples were held either on ice or returned to the refrigerator.

Waste characterization samples (i.e., TCLP and reactivity, ignitibility and corrosivity) were collected from 22 sediment cores (one from each of the 17 pre-planned individual core locations and 5 of the contingency locations) to support the evaluation of remedial alternative in the FS. These samples were composites representing material along the length of the cores. Two composite samples of investigation-derived waste (IDW) were submitted to characterize the wastes for disposal.

The sediment samples were submitted for the following analyses:

- Low Soil Volatile Organic Compounds by EPA CLP SOM01.2
- Low Soil Semi-volatile Organic Compounds by EPA CLP SOM01.2
- Soil Pesticides by EPA CLP SOM01.2
- Soil Polychlorinated Biphenyls by EPA CLP SOM01.2
- Inductively-coupled plasma-atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) Metals by EPA CLP ILM05.4
- Mercury by EPA CLP ILM05.4
- Cyanide by EPA CLP ILM05.4
- Wet Chemistry (TOC) by Walkley Black
- Wet Chemistry (Total Sulfide) by SW-846 9030B/9034
- Grainsize by ASTM D4464

The waste characterization and IDW samples were submitted for TCLPV, TCLPS, TCLPP, TCLPH, TCLPM to support 40 CFR 261-24, reactivity (cyanide, sulfide), corrosivity (pH), and ignitibility (Pensky Martens).

An aliquot for archival was also collected from each sampling interval and will be held frozen for up to one year in case future analyses are needed. In instances where greater than 6 feet of native sediment was recovered, selected samples were collected from deeper intervals per EPA request.

Table D2 includes a summary of the thickness of native sediment sampled from each location. The sediment core logs, and photographic logs of all cores collected along transects are included as attachments. Photos taken of the sediment cores during the characterization process and are provided electronically.

The analytical laboratories used are listed below. The USEPA CLP Case Number for his investigation was 39452.

Sample Type	Name and Address of Laboratory
TAL Metals + Mercury & Cyanide, TCL VOC, Archive, and TCLP Metals	Liberty Analytical Corporation (LIBERTY) 501 Madison Avenue Cary, NC 27513 (919) 379-4080
TCL Pesticides, TCL PCBs, TCLP VOCs, BNA, Herbicides, Pesticides, PCBs, TCL SVOCs	Mitkem Corporation (MITKEM) 175 Metro Center Blvd Warwick, RI 02886 (401) 732-3400
TCL SVOCs	DataChem Laboratories, Inc 960 West LeVoy Drive Salt Lake City, UT 84123 (801) 266-7700
TOC, grainsize, sulfide	Test America Burlington 30 Community Drive, Suite 11 South Burlington, VT 05403 (802) 660-1990
Reactivity, corrosivity and ignitibility	Test America Westfield 53 Southampton Rd. Westfield, MA 01085 (413) 572-4000

Sediment Grab Sample Collection

In addition to the sediment coring activities, a surface sediment grab sample was collected from location 37B per EPA request. This location was scheduled to be sampled during surface sediment sampling event scheduled for the next phase of field work. However, this station is located beneath a gravel barge docked at the Ferrara Brothers concrete facility and arrangements had been made for the barge to be moved to access sampling locations for the sediment coring event. A grab sample was collected at the same location as the sediment core sample because soft material was encountered at the sediment surface.

This sample was collected using a petite Ponar grab sampler with a 6 inch square opening. Sediment from the grab was emptied into a dedicated, disposable aluminum pan and was sampled as described above. The grab sample was submitted for all TAL/TCL parameters, sulfide, TOC, and grainsize. An extra sample jar was archived.

EPA Emergency Response Team (ERT) Coring Investigation

The EPA-ERT performed a coring investigation in January 2010 to specifically target sampling locations that may not have been accessible once NYC DEP had started installation of the aeration pipe as part of the Flushing Tunnel rehabilitation project. The EPA-ERT collected cores from 10 locations in the northern reach of the canal from January 27 through January 29, 2010. The same vibracoring subcontractor, sample collection and processing methods, and analytical scheme were utilized as previously described; however, these 10 sediment cores were collected to a maximum depth of 16 feet below the sediment surface and a different sampling interval was utilized. Samples were collected from 0.0 to 0.5 feet, 0.5 to 1.0 feet, and at 1 foot intervals thereafter. The core logs from this sampling event have been included as an Attachment to this appendix.

Field Observations, Field Changes, and Challenges

The vessel was initially positioned on, or as near to the target location as field conditions allowed. The sampling location was then adjusted based on field conditions, such as the presence of large debris, shoreline features or obstructions that interfered with positioning (such as the aeration pipe), or unsuccessful initial coring attempts. These field adjustments resulted in some of the as-sampled locations being off-set from the planned targets; however, the objectives of this sampling investigation were still met and the data are expected to be sufficient to complete the RI/FS process.

The primary challenges encountered during this sampling event were due to the presence of debris within the canal that interfered with core collection. In many areas, the bulkheads are in disrepair and pieces of the bulkheads, along with other debris, have fallen into the canal. Large accumulations of debris were also prevalent where streets ended at the canal. Within the turning basins, debris consisted of sunken barges, old dock structures, tires, and metal from adjacent scrap recycling operations.

Gravel also covered the bottom of the canal downstream of the Ferrara Brothers concrete facility to below the 9th Street Bridge. Gravel was also noted beneath the barges at New York City asphalt facility southeast of the Gowanus Expressway. The presence of gravel in these locations resulted in difficulty collecting sediment cores, including reduced penetration, bent and broken core barrels, and very low sediment recoveries.

Minor adjustments were made at many sampling locations based on field conditions (e.g., debris or obstructions, refusal or unacceptable cores, and access and vessel positioning considerations). A summary of the more significant position modifications and the associated rationale is presented below.

Sampling locations 112 and 113 were adjusted based on field observations to be aligned with New York City CSOs. Sediment cores were collected directly in front of the outfalls or as near as field conditions would allow.

Location 37B was sampled west of the initial target due to presence of gravel throughout this entire area. The vessel was initially positioned at the target and sediment probing indicated a very dense layer of gravel. The vessel was slowly moved to the west until the crew determined that there was an increased likelihood of obtaining a usable sample. The final, as-sampled location of 37B was positioned in front of a small outfall on the northern bulkhead.

Sampling location 37B. Bulkhead is damp near outfall as a result of sampling activities (e.g., washing deck off).

Cores collected at locations 133, 134, and 135, positioned immediately south of the Hamilton Avenue bridge, did not penetrate into native sediment. The cores were likely refused due to either debris or deposits of gravel or concrete related to the bridge construction. Locations 9B and 15A were not sampled during this event per EPA request. The EPA Emergency Response Team (ERT) had sampled these locations during an the investigation in January 2010.

A large expanse of debris was encountered on the west side of the canal to the south of Hamilton Avenue. There is evidence that an old bulkhead may have collapsed from the area north of location 70B to south of location 73E. Vibracoring attempts in this area were generally met with very shallow refusal on what was assumed to be debris. The coring attempts at location 136 were started near the shoreline and were progressively moved toward the center of the channel. Contingency coring location 150, at the end of Hackett Street, was positioned slightly further from shore during the first coring attempt in an effort to recover both accumulated and native sediment.

The eastern and western shorelines are armored with cobble-sized material or large rip-rap in the Gowanus Bay area. As a result, the sediment surface in many areas along the shorelines is also covered with this material. Locations 139, 141, and 144 were adjusted in the field by moving further from shore and nearer to the center of the channel, in order to penetrate into the accumulated and native sediments.

Contingency location 148 was positioned as close as practicable to the bulkhead; however, due to the presence of the aeration pipe and the shoreline geometry in this area the as-sampled location is off-set from the bulkhead.

Sediment Coring Summary

Sediment cores were collected from all the planned locations except for 9B and 15A, which were previously sampled by the EPA in January 2010. A total of 255 coring attempts were required to collect cores from 133 unique locations. A total of 516 unique sediment samples were submitted for chemical analyses.

The objectives of this sampling event were met, except in instances where field conditions prevented recovery of 6 feet of native sediment (Table 4). The locations where the target thickness of native material was not recovered were generally in three areas:

- Locations where the soft sediment thickness was greater than 14 feet and the depth of penetration was limited by core barrel length of 20 feet (e.g., at the head of the canal and in the 11th Street turning basin)
- Locations where the sediment surface was covered with gravel (e.g., the entire channel south of the Ferrara Brothers facility to south of the 9th Street bridge, and the area adjacent to the New York City asphalt plant south of Hamilton Avenue).

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- Locations in areas where widespread debris was present (e.g., stations positioned near the ends of streets, stations along the west side of the channel downstream of the Hamilton Avenue bridge).

References

GEI Corporation (GEI). 2007. Draft Remedial Investigation Technical Report. Prepared for KeySpan Corporation. April.